

SPHINX Dissemination Activities Report v2

WP8– Dissemination, sustainability and exploitation

Version: 1.00

SPHINX

A Universal Cyber Security Toolkit for
Health-Care Industry

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Executive Summary

SPHINX aims to introduce a Universal Cyber Security Toolkit, to enhance the cyber protection of Health IT Ecosystem and ensure the privacy and integrity of patients' data. The dissemination and communication of the project constitute a pivotal aspect of its overall planning, due to their role on promoting SPHINX's intentions, scope and contributions to the field of cybersecurity. Hence, the project adopts a multifaceted and detailed dissemination plan from the very beginning in order to:

- Create awareness about the SPHINX Solution benefits and opportunities.
- Increase engagement and encourage involvement of the target groups in the project activities.
- Ensure sustainability of the SPHINX targeted audience after the project's completion.

The present deliverable describes the progress and provides statistics of the dissemination and communication activities, both online and offline, during the second year of the Project (M13-M24). This is the second version of the Dissemination Activities Report, a deliverable that is scheduled to be annually conducted.

The chapters below feature data regarding the visual branding of the Project website, the website and the social media channels created for SPHINX, the networking activities of Consortium Members and the scientific publications of Project as well as the press releases, newsletters, videos, and blog entries produced.

At this point, it should be noted that due to the unprecedented global conditions caused by the Covid-19 pandemic, the predefined action plans for dissemination and communication of the project have been changed. As a result of travel bans and local restrictions and/or lockdowns project's efforts have been shifted towards online material promotion, virtual representation of SPHINX and partners engagement in relevant virtual events.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

The present deliverable is the second annual report of the activities implemented by Consortium Members to disseminate and communicate SPHINX. In particular, the deliverable entails descriptions and data regarding the progress of the defined dissemination and communication planning. Also, it critically analyses relative results through the second year of SPHINX, to suggest how the next steps of the action plan for the dissemination of SPHINX are going to be deployed.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The Dissemination Activities Report v2 is structured to provide feedback on the dissemination and communication planning as it has been elaborated on the SPHINX's Dissemination Plan. Hence, the following sections are based on the content of D8.2. SPHINX Dissemination Plan. In this way, the current document aims to produce an accurate form of reporting which will be clearly aligned with the approach of the dissemination strategy of the Project. Below, the dissemination and communication activities of the Project are clustered in respective sections to assess their efficiency to meet the objectives of the dissemination strategy. This main part of the report is titled Periodic Report. The deliverable concludes with a display of an aggregate table in which the objectives of SPHINX's dissemination strategy, as they have been derived from Project's Grant Agreement, are summarised and presented.

2 Periodic Report

2.1 Project Branding

Building upon the visual identity that was shaped during the first year, the project has moved forwards to more specialised content creation as part of its virtual representation. After the completion of the awareness building phase in the first year, the aim throughout the second year of the project was to provide the target audiences information suitable for a deeper understanding of SPHINX scope and the work of the Consortium Members. As a result, an infographic presenting the project's ID has been designed and a series of videos has been uploaded at SPHINX's YouTube channel.

2.1.1 Infographic

In order to deliver a comprehensive and well-rounded overview of SPHINX for the needs of multiple presentations of project partners, an infographic has been crafted. The design depicts SPHINX's ID information such as project description, objectives, the pilot sites, consortium members, the proper declaration of EU funding by Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme and its duration. Moreover, the infographic depicts an easy-to-grasp design of the architecture of SPHINX Toolkit.

The full-size infographic is available in Annex I.

2.1.2 SPHINX Flyer (Greek Version)

During the first trimester of project's second year, a Greek version of an informative and awareness raising flyer was printed. The flyer was finalised by the end of the project's first implementation year and it was subsequently, shared in the Greek pilot sites of SPHINX, that is, the premises of 5th Regional Health Authority of Thessaly and Stereo, the University Hospital of Larissa and the General Hospital of Volos in March 2020.

The action aimed at informing the medical and, even more, the administrative staffs of the Organisations about the day-to-day activities that they need to keep in mind to maintain a cybersafe work routine. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic and the overload of Healthcare Organisations, the action was not replicated at Romanian and Portuguese pilot sites as it was initially intended. Partners have agreed to re-plan the action as soon as the situation is eased in the pilot sites.

The full-size flyer is available in Annex II.

2.1.3 Videos

The project has put emphasis on knowledge diffusion and especially on disseminating technical information about what tools and methods are being utilised to set up the SPHINX Toolkit. Hence, after the completion of the first iteration of the components that comprise the envisioned solution, a series of short presentations and demonstrations has been recorded.

Every component inside SPHINX's architecture has been presented in an approximately 5 minutes video by the respective project partner that is leading its development. The videos are accessible through project's website in a dedicated [vault](#) and through SPHINX channel on [YouTube](#).

Moving forward, the aim is to make these videos widely visible and use them as information resources on future project dissemination actions, such as upcoming newsletter issues, partners' presentations on events and/or exploitation activities, social media campaigns.

2.2 Online Metrics

The online dissemination and communication of SPHINX is based on two streams. On the one hand, project's website has been set as a point of reference and a source of information about SPHINX. On the other hand, the social media accounts of SPHINX are drawing content from project's development and the activities of partners and promote it to varying audiences in a direct and engaging fashion.

2.2.1 Project Website

SPHINX website operates as a central dissemination and communication tool of the project providing the main results of the SPHINX research and outcomes. During the second year of the project, emphasis was put on creating diverse content to enrich the created pages and feature enough information for the multiple aspects of SPHINX. Notably, there is weekly blog entry on SPHINX's website, whose content derives from original work of project partners in their respective deliverable reports or from their dissemination activities (more information is provided in the Media Content Sub-chapter).

The website is available at: <https://sphinx-project.eu/>

YEAR TWO ANALYTICS

The following data are sourced by Google Analytics to assess the progress of the website throughout the second year of the project.

Overall, 2,978 users have visited SPHINX website, while their majority were new visitors, which indicates that the project has gained additional visibility during the reported period. Still the aim for a greater volume of returning audiences remains for the upcoming year.

Regarding their activity on the website, users have been engaged with SPHINX's content in a total of 4,043 sessions, a number that has been increased from last year (3,015 sessions during Year 1). Analytics define sessions as the period time a user is actively engaged with a website, app, etc. All usage data (Screen Views, Events, Ecommerce, etc.) is associated with a session. Moreover, each user averaged nearly one and a half sessions and they viewed approximately 2 pages (2.80) per session, which lasted on an average of 2 minutes and 21 seconds. In sum, users who visited SPHINX website have recorded 9,038 pageviews.

Figure 1. SPHINX Website – Audience Overview

Tracing where the users visit SPHINX from shows a shift on audience demographics, as the United States are on the top of the list for the second year of the project, only to be followed closely by Greece. Audiences from additional EU countries, like Germany, Netherlands and France, have emerged higher in the list thus providing further evidence of a change in regard to website's visibility. The goal for the next year is to solidify viewership across European countries, and mainly from countries represented inside SPHINX Consortium.

	Country	Users	% Users
1.	United States	686	22.98%
2.	Greece	666	22.31%
3.	Netherlands	139	4.66%
4.	Germany	135	4.52%
5.	Portugal	106	3.55%
6.	France	103	3.45%
7.	Finland	90	3.02%
8.	India	87	2.91%
9.	China	86	2.88%
10.	United Kingdom	81	2.71%

Figure 2. SPHINX Website - Audience Countries

2.2.2 Social Media Accounts

ViLabs is managing the three social media accounts that have been created for SPHINX project. Namely, these are Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn. Their content comes mainly from project's website updates (i.e., a new blog entry is posted every week in website and then it is promoted to all social media accounts) and from news about cybersecurity in healthcare. What is more, the social media accounts are used to promote further dissemination activities of SPHINX and other Synergy projects (i.e., newsletters, events, publications, etc.).

At this point, it should be noted that SPHINX social media accounts were being updated on a daily basis throughout the second year of the project, in order to increase project's visibility in online social networks.

YEAR TWO ANALYTICS

Facebook

The Facebook page of SPHINX, Sphinx-project.eu, has accumulated 716 followers by the end of the second year of the project. The daily activity of the page helped to increase the overall followership and grow a dedicated audience, which stays engaged with the project's updates.

Figure 3. SPHINX Facebook page

To understand the nature of the audience of SPHINX, additional data from ‘Facebook Insights’ tool have been examined.

As a result, purposeful statistics about the project’s Facebook page are elaborated.

During the second year of SPHINX, the audience has remained gender balanced within all the age cohorts (see Figure 4); while more than half of the followership comes from Greece (See Figure 5). Therefore, the goal for the upcoming year of SPHINX is to maintain the balance in terms of female/male ratio and gain followership from additional countries of project partners.

Figure 4. SPHINX Facebook Page - Followers Demographics

Country	Your followers	Language	Your followers
Greece	424	Greek	349
Romania	40	English (US)	92
Bulgaria	31	English (UK)	57
Albania	24	Romanian	30
Ukraine	21	Albanian	29
Portugal	20	Bulgarian	28
Serbia	19	Russian	18
Kosovo	18	Serbian	17
Germany	10	Portuguese (Portugal)	17
Bosnia & Herzegovina	10	Croatian	16

Figure 5. SPHINX Facebook Page - Followers Countries & Languages

Twitter

The @ProjectSphinx is the project's account on Twitter and stands as the most followed social media channel SPHINX with 770 followers.

Figure 6. SPHINX Twitter Account

According to the Analytics service of the platform, the account has accumulated more than two hundred thousand impressions and approximately two and a half thousand users have visited SPHINX profile (see Figure 7). Hence the above, the daily update of the account with cybersecurity news and project's developments, likewise Facebook, has resulted to a significant visibility of the project on this social network.

Figure 7. SPHINX Twitter Account - Analytics Summary

LinkedIn

The LinkedIn profile of SPHINX, titled sphinx-project, is the third social media account that the project utilises. The scope of the LinkedIn profile is to address a smaller audience, yet more familiar with SPHINX's purpose. The reason is that the followers' background is more related to the cybersecurity domain due to their job functions. Overall, the followership of LinkedIn profile has progressed a small increase through year Two, reaching the 98 users.

Figure 8. SPHINX LinkedIn Profile

However, the significant element of SPHINX's LinkedIn audience lies, as argued above, to the professional domains, from which the followers come. As depicted in the Figures 9 and 10 below, the profession of many LinkedIn users that follow SPHINX project is related to engineering, IT and research above others and many of them are employed in IT Services and/or Research domains. These statistics ensure that the cybersecurity updates and the posts about SPHINX development reach adequate stakeholder audiences.

Figure 9. SPHINX LinkedIn Profile - Followers per Profession

Figure 10. SPHINX LinkedIn Profile - Followers per Industry

2.3 Networking Activities

As stated above, the global circumstances impacted project’s plans in regard to dissemination and communication activities. Networking activities took a toll since several events were taken out of the schedule due to either postponement or cancelation. As a result, SPHINX partners sought to represent the project on available virtual events. What is more, the project was able to organise its own online workshop and attract a great volume of audience consisting of IT experts employed in the broad Healthcare Sector.

Hence the above, SPHINX managed to stay active and in touch with its Stakeholder audiences. As the project enters its final year, there are more events in the pipeline to be organised either by SPHINX partners and/or in collaboration with other projects in the form of synergy.

2.3.1 SPHINX Workshop

SPHINX Consortium member DYPE5, the fifth Greek Regional Health Authority, hosted a workshop that was dedicated to IT personnel of Healthcare organisations in order to raise their awareness regarding contemporary cybersecurity matters.

The workshop was titled [CYBERAWARE4HEALTH](#) and took place virtually on Wednesday, 16 December 2020. Partners from National Technical University of Greece, PDMFC and ViLabs contributed to the event with

presentations about information security, risk management, necessary daily actions for a cyber secure routine, firewalls concepts and the Sphinx Toolkit. These presentations were delivered in three sessions.

What is more, Mrs. Dimitra Livery, Network and Information Security expert of the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA), gave a keynote speech on procurement guidelines for cybersecurity in hospitals and medical centres.

The event gathered more than 100 attendees from several Healthcare Organisations, mainly from Greece, and from other countries of Consortium Members such as Portugal. The audience consisted of IT professionals, middle and high-level managers of IT departments, thus allowing the project to engage with an audience of potential end-users.

2.3.2 Synergies

Following the introduction to European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures (ECSCI), SPHINX has taken part in the [first online workshop of the Cluster](#) along with ten more Horizon 2020 projects that are active on the broad sector of cyber and physical security of critical infrastructures across Europe. Again, due to ongoing limitations the event was eventually held in a virtual format.

The workshop formally kicked-off the Cluster activities and its context referred to the different approaches on integrated (i.e. cyber and physical) security in seven different industrial sectors, that is finance, healthcare, energy, air transport communications, gas, and water. The peculiarities of critical infrastructure protection in each one of these sectors were discussed and addressed by the different projects of the ECSCI cluster that presented their outcomes, discussing the technical, ethical and societal aspects and the underlying technologies.

The Hellenic Mediterranean University contributed to this synergy Event representing SPHINX project.

Moreover, SPHINX project established synergy with the [Cyberwatching.eu](#), the European observatory of research and innovation in the field of cybersecurity and privacy. Funded under the European Commission's H2020 programme, Cyberwatching.eu is an online portal that contributes to making the Digital Single Market a safer place by promoting the uptake and understanding of cutting-edge cybersecurity and privacy services which emerge from Research and Innovation initiatives across Europe.

As a result of the contact, SPHINX is now featured in the research hub of Cyberwatching.eu and is managing its own dedicated [project page](#). SPHINX page provides an overview of the project and informs the users about the expected impacts and the pilot actions planned. In addition, the page is used as an additional repository of SPHINX deliverables and videos. This way, ongoing project's results are visible to a broad community of experts, consisting of cybersecurity researchers, European project managers and Industry Stakeholders.

As SPHINX is entering its final year, it is planned to leverage more promotional features of the Cyberwatching.eu portal, such as “the Project of the Month” or the “Provider of the Week”, that are provided in order to maximise the visibility of project's outcomes.

2.3.3 Events organised by 3rd parties

Despite the general slowdown to the organisation of real-life events, SPHINX partners have worked to meet the requirements of the networking activities by representing the project in virtual events. What is more, the effort for the second year of project's implementation has been put towards the engagement of SPHINX partners with Stakeholders of Policy Sector, to make additional progress with this type of external target audience, as it was documented and indicated by the first version of the Dissemination Activities Report regarding the first year of SPHINX.

Below, the events organised by third parties, where SPHINX partners participated are enlisted:

- Networking between Industry, Research Organisations and Policy-making Stakeholders during the [SMI2G Brokerage Event](#) in Brussels, Belgium by **EDGE**.
- Presentation of SPHINX solution to Policy Officers and Medical Sector representatives during the annual [Greek Health IT 2020 Conference](#) held online by **DYPE5**.
- Engagement with Policy-making Stakeholders at Inception Meeting of the EU Health Information Sharing and Analysis Centre (ISAC) held online by **DYPE5 and HES**.
- Participation to the [XV International Industrial Cybersecurity Experiences Congress](#) held online by **TECNALIA**.
- Networking between Industry, Research Organisations and Policy-making Stakeholders during the three rounds of ICT Verticals and Horizontals for Blockchain Standardisation roundtable discussions held online by **TECNALIA**.
- Promotion of upcoming SPHINX workshop during the Cyberwatching.eu webinar [Security and Privacy by Design for Healthcare](#) held online by **ViLabs**.

2.4 Project Publications

SPHINX is aligned with the respective guidelines of Horizon 2020 programme in terms of knowledge diffusion. For this purpose, during its second year, the project continued disclosing the public deliverable reports conducted by the partners in adequate channels and managed to produce three scientific publications. What is more, additional scientific publications are elaborated while this report is being written.

2.4.1 Deliverable Reports

The dedicated [SPHINX community in Zenodo](#) was kept updated. That is, public deliverables were uploaded at the platform after their timely submission, to maintain the repository of technical and scientific knowledge produced by SPHINX partners.

2.4.2 Scientific Publications

During the second year of SPHINX, project partners from HMU and AiDEAS have successfully published two more scientific articles. The material, which is accessible via open access, is listed as follows:

- Stoyanova, M., Nicolaides's, Y., Panagiotis, S., Palls, E., & Markakis, E. K. (2020). A Survey on the Internet of Things (IoT) Forensics: Challenges, Approaches and Open Issues. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*. [10.1109/COMST.2019.2962586](#)
- Moustakidis, S., & Karlsson, P. (2020). A novel feature extraction methodology using Siamese convolutional neural networks for intrusion detection. *Cybersecurity*, 3(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42400-020-00056-4>

In addition, a significant accomplishment in regard to scientific publications has been the contribution of a chapter dedicated to SPHINX Toolkit in the publication of the Open Access book “Cyber-Physical Threat intelligence”. The book has been a collaborative outcome of a synergy between several European projects that are active on the board sector of cybersecurity for critical infrastructures.

Partners from EDGE, NTUA and ViLabs have co-authored the chapter; below the full citation is given:

- Manso, M., Guerra, B., Doukas, G., & Mountz, V. Innovative Toolkit to Assess and Mitigate Cyber Threats in the Healthcare Sector. In John Soldati's (ed.), James Philpot (ed.), Gabriele Giunta (ed.) (2020), "Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence for Critical Infrastructures Security: A Guide to Integrated Cyber-Physical Protection of Modern Critical Infrastructures", Boston-Delft: now publishers, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1561/9781680836875>

Overall, this synergy book has achieved a significant impact with quite more than 10,000 downloads (approx. 13,500 by the time this report is written). As a result, a second volume of the book is being discussed among editors and the publishing organisation and SPHINX partners are on board.

2.5 Media Content

For the second year of SPHINX, the dissemination effort regarding media content creation has been placed mainly on the creation of plenty of blog entries to project's website; a task which derives from the target indicators of SPHINX's Grant Agreement.

2.5.1 Promo video for Pilot Cases (Greece)

In order to foster general awareness about SPHINX pilot demonstrations, the project has opted to create short promotional videos at each pilot site. The aim of this activity is to inform medical and administrative staff of the pilot sites, as well as regional stakeholders about SPHINX project and its application, thus facilitating trust and potential uptake after project's completion.

To this end, the first video was created in the premises of University Hospital of Larissa, Greece which is going to be one of the infrastructures that the 5th Regional Health Authority of Thessaly and Stereo will provide for the Toolkit evaluation. The video is available at [SPHINX's YouTube channel](#), and it is also featured at project's website on the Greek pilot [page](#).

2.5.2 Newsletter

In order to meet the expected targets, SPHINX circulated two more newsletter issues within its second year. On the one hand, the project published its [second Newsletter Issue](#) on July and another [H2020 Synergy Newsletter](#) on December.

2.5.3 Blog entries

SPHINX has put significant effort to enrich the Blog section of its website making it a great resource of information about project's developments. Content is being added in a weekly basis and it is subsequently promoted on project's social media channels. The blog entries mainly provide information from SPHINX public deliverables and, also, refer to SPHINX's presence in various networking events.

By the time this report is being conducted, there are 55 blog entries on SPHINX's website dedicated [page](#), thus exceeding the target number for the second year and providing a good foundation to reach the overall expected number by the end of the project.

2.5.4 Workshop Presentations

Following the successful organisation of CYBERAWARE4HEALTH online workshop, all the presentations have been uploaded at SPHINX YouTube channels into a [dedicated playlist](#), so that the content is openly available on demand. All the contributors have previously given their consent for this dissemination option.

3 Summary Table M13 – M24

The following table is an aggregate outline of the dissemination and communication actions that were carried through during the second year of SPHINX's lifecycle. This period corresponds to M13 – M24 of SPHINX and the clustering below is organised according to the goals setting included in the Grant Agreement of the Project. The table summarises what is discussed in the above Periodic Progress Chapter.

Dissemination & Communication Objectives	Activity	Achievements	Grant Agreement Goals - Year Two
Create Project Identity and Branding	Project Logo, Colour Scheme, Templates	Infographic designed & used during project presentations	Revise Branding and Identity as required by project partners
Design Dissemination Materials	Brochure, Poster	Pilot Case Promo video created	Update materials according to project feedback. Create versions in other languages where possible with project partners.
Create Project Website	Website	Project website updated with further information about SPHINX aspects	Update the website with portal information and open data repository.
Social Media Strategy	Number of Video/Slideshow	19 component demonstration videos, 6 project workshop presentations videos	YouTube - 3 Videos live w. 5000 hits
	Facebook Followers	716	3000
	Twitter Followers	770	3000
	LinkedIn Followers	98	N/A
Networking events and workshops	Total:	7	Attend and/or host up to 5 relevant networking events or workshops addressing the target communities, stakeholders and users.
	Organisation of a Workshop	1	
	Participation to a Conference	2	
	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop (Exhibitions, Networking events, Symposia, Webinars, etc.)	4	
Generate positive media coverage & releasing project publications	Newsletter	2	2 Newsletters
	Scientific and peer reviewed publication (article and/or papers and/or presentation)	3	4-8 project publications
	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication) (Blog entries)	55	At least 50 blog entries
Cluster with Relevant Projects & initiatives	Cluster with relevant projects and/or global initiatives	Participated in ECSCI Cluster 1 st Workshop, Created project's page in Cyberwatching.eu platform	Cluster with 2 relevant projects or global initiatives

Annex I: SPHINX Infographic

SPHINX A Universal Cybersecurity Toolkit for the Healthcare Industry

GOALS

SPHINX aims to introduce a **health tailored Universal Cybersecurity Toolkit**, thus enhancing **cyber protection of the Health and care IT Ecosystem** and ensuring patient data privacy and integrity.

OBJECTIVES

- Cyber protection and data privacy and integrity
- Proactive assessment and mitigation of Cybersecurity threats
- Evaluation and verification of new Medical Devices & Services
- Provision of the SPHINX Certification
- Near real-time vulnerability assessment of operating IT Ecosystems

PILOTS

- 📍 **Greece:** University Hospital of Larissa & General Hospital of Volos
- 📍 **Portugal:** Hospital do Espirito Santo
- 📍 **Romania:** Polaris Medical Clinical

- Starting Date:** 1/1/2019
- Project Duration:** 36 months
- EC funding:** € 4,999,435
- 17 partners / 9 EU countries**

- 🌐 www.sphinx-project.eu
- 🐦 ProjectSphinx
- 🌐 sphinx-project

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 826183

Healthcare IT Operational Environment

Annex II: SPHINX Flyer (Greek version)

Σύμφωνα με τον **N.4577/2018 (Α'199)**, βάσει του οποίου ενσωματώθηκε στην Ελληνική νομοθεσία η **Οδηγία 2016/1148/ΕΕ** του Ευρωπαϊκού Κοινοβουλίου και του Συμβουλίου σχετικά με μέτρα για υψηλό κοινό επίπεδο ασφάλειας συστημάτων δικτύου και πληροφοριών σε ολόκληρη την Ένωση και στο πλαίσιο της συμμετοχής στο **Ευρωπαϊκό Έργο SPHINX** για την κυβερνοασφάλεια στον τομέα της Υγείας, η 5η Υγειονομική Περιφέρεια Θεσσαλίας & Στερεάς Ελλάδας **σας συμβουλεύει:**

Αλλάζετε τακτικά τους κωδικούς πρόσβασης (passwords) και μην τους μοιράζετε με τρίτους

Κρατάτε αντίγραφα ασφαλείας κρίσιμων δεδομένων σας

Μην ανοίγετε αλληλογραφία και συνδέσμους από άγνωστο αποστολέα και ελέγχετε πάντα τη διεύθυνση αποστολέα. Μπορεί να περιέχουν ιούς

Μην αφήνετε τρίτους να χρησιμοποιούν τους υπολογιστές της Περιφέρειας

Κλειδώνετε τον υπολογιστή σας όταν φεύγετε από το γραφείο σας

Μην εισάγετε USB στον υπολογιστή σας χωρίς την έγκριση της Διεύθυνσης Πληροφορικής

Με τη χρηματοδότηση του προγράμματος της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης "Horizon2020" σύμφωνα με το συμβόλαιο No. 826183

